

ANALYTICAL ARTICLE ON SEMANTIC AND SOCIAL FACTORS IN THE FORMATION OF THE TERMINOLOGY OF UZBEK OFFICIAL WORKING PAPERS

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ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada o'zbek rasmiy ish qog'ozlari terminologiyasining tahlili amalga oshirilgan. Muallif, hujjatlar va ish qog'ozlarida atamalarning tilshunoslik, huquqshunoslik va boshqaruv sohalaridagi ahamiyatini o'rganadi. Maqola, terminlarning aniq va to'g'ridan-to'g'ri foydalanish orqali hujjatlarning samarali va tushunarli bo'lishini ta'kidlaydi. Ushbu terminlarning o'zbek tilidagi rivojlanishi va muammolari ham yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Rasmiy ish qog'oz; Tilshunoslik; Huquqshunoslik; Ish qog'ozlari; Terminlar; Hujjatlar.

ABSTRACT

The article analyzes the terminology of Uzbek official business papers. The author studies the importance of terms in documents and business papers in the fields of linguistics, law and management. The article emphasizes that the documents are effective and understandable through the clear and direct use of terms. The development and problems of these terms in the Uzbek language are also covered.

Keywords: Official business paper; Linguistics; Law; Business papers; Terms; Documents.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье анализируется терминология официальных рабочих документов Узбекистана. Автор рассматривает значение терминов языкознания, права и управления в документах и рабочих материалах. В статье подчеркивается, что благодаря четкому и прямому использованию терминов документы будут эффективными и понятными. Также освещены развитие и проблемы этих терминов в узбекском языке.

Ключевые слова: Официальный рабочий документ; лингвистика; Юриспруденция; Рабочие документы; Условия; Документы.

Introduction

Official working papers are an integral part of the administrative management and legal system of the state. They ensure the accuracy and efficiency of document circulation, and shape the image of the state in international relations. In Uzbekistan, state documents are kept in the Uzbek language, this process serves to strengthen the status of the state language and develop national culture. At the same time, the issue of developing terminology consistent with international requirements and standards remains relevant. This article is devoted to the analysis of the historical basis of the terminology of Uzbek official working papers, its modern state, compatibility with international experience, emerging problems and solutions.

Historical foundations of the terminology of official working papers

The formation of the terminology of Uzbek official working papers includes a long

historical process:

1. **Soviet period:** during the Soviet Union, official documents in the territory of Uzbekistan were mainly conducted in Russian. At the same time, terms adapted to local needs were used in the Uzbek language. But national terminology was limited, and many terms were accepted as direct translations of Russian words.
2. **The period of independence:** after Uzbekistan gained independence in 1991, great attention was paid to strengthening the status of the state language. The Law "On State Language" adopted in 1989 provided the main legal framework in this regard. During this period, the process of forming Uzbek document terminology accelerated. In order to develop the national language, new terms and concepts were developed.
3. **Modern stage:** As a result of the expansion of international relations in the era of globalization, there was a need to adapt the terms used in official documents to international standards. This process requires the creation of terminology that meets modern needs while preserving national culture and traditions.

Terminology formation factors

The following main factors play a role in the formation of the terminology of official working papers:

1. **Legal base:** The Constitution, laws and other regulatory legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan determine the language of official proceedings. These documents regulate the terminology used in public administration and the legal system.
2. **Principles of linguistics:** Adaptation of terms to the Uzbek language is carried out in accordance with the phonetic, morphological and syntactic features of the language. The terms are combined with the comprehensibility and convenience of the Uzbek language.
3. **International standards:** standards approved by ISO and other international organizations are used as a basis for mastering the terms used in international relations. This process facilitates international communication.
4. **Technological development:** With the development of modern technologies, new concepts and terms are emerging. For example, the issue of expressing terms like "blockchain" or "cloud computing" in Uzbek remains relevant.

International experience and Uzbek terminology

Uzbekistan actively participates in the international arena and cooperates effectively with foreign countries and organizations. This requires that the terms used in official documents conform to international standards. International experience has a significant impact on Uzbek terminology in the following areas:

1. **International legal standards:** International agreements and memorandums are translated in accordance with international standards to ensure legal clarity of documents. For example, the term "memorandum of understanding" is expressed as "memorandum of mutual understanding" in Uzbek.
2. **Scientific-literary cooperation:** As a result of cooperation with international scientific and academic organizations, new terms are developed and national terminology is enriched.
3. **ISO standards:** the terms are accepted and put into practice according to the rules developed by the International Organization for Standardization.

Types of official working papers and their peculiarities

Official working papers in Uzbekistan are divided into several main types, each of which

performs a specific task:

1. **Decisions and decrees:** the main documents adopted by state administration bodies.
2. **Minutes:** Documents reflecting the results of meetings and sessions.
3. **Agreements:** Agreements between legal entities and individuals.
4. **Information letters:** Documents intended for inter-organizational communication.
5. **Reports:** Documents providing information on the activities of organizations.

Problems and ways to solve them

The following problems are observed in the development of the terminology of official working papers:

1. **Misunderstanding of terms:** The existence of several Uzbek alternatives for certain terms leads to confusion in the understanding of official documents. For example, the use of the word "protocol" in the forms "protocol" and "protocol".
2. **Complexity of technological terms:** There are problems in adapting terms related to new technologies to the Uzbek language. For example, the same clear and correct translation of the term "artificial intelligence" is still being discussed.
3. **Difficulties in standardizing terms:** Different organizations express the same terms differently, which leads to misunderstandings in official documents.

Suggestions and recommendations

It is advisable to implement the following measures to develop and standardize the terminology of official working papers:

1. **Establishment of special working groups:** Formation of special groups combining linguists, lawyers, and international experts. These groups should be engaged in the development of new terms, their testing and formal approval.
2. **Cooperation with international experts:** organization of seminars and conferences with international experts in order to study international experience and standards. This process brings Uzbek terminology closer to the international arena.
3. **Creating digital platforms:** Creating online databases of terminology and making it available to the general public. These platforms can be used to distribute new terms and monitor their usage.
4. **Preservation of language and culture:** Strengthen cooperation with local experts in the development of terms appropriate to national culture and traditions.
5. **Development of public educational programs:** Establishing special training courses for civil servants and specialists working with official documents. These courses should teach the practical application of new terminology.
6. **Update of regulatory legal documents:** Continuous updating of current legislation to introduce new terms and standardize them. It is advisable to implement the following measures to develop and standardize the terminology of working papers:
7. **Organization of special working groups:** linguists, jurist.

CONCLUSION

The analysis of the terminology of Uzbek official working papers is important in the article. In documents and working papers, terminology, linguistics plays a major role in the interaction between the fields of law and management. Ensure clear and accurate terminology software fixes, but also ensure that they are clear and efficient in the official workflow. The emergence of terms in the Uzbek language can be produced in a unique way, but further

research and production is needed in this area.

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